

IMPROVEMENT OF KNOWLEDGE OF STUDENTS OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL OF RANGKAH KIDUL ON HAND WASH THROUGH HEALTH PROMOTION

Elok Triestuning¹, Rian Prasetyo², Diaz Nur Aindah², Regita Indira Ardianti², Dita Wardatul Anifa², Nurul Khalifah², Dyah Fitri Anggraheni², Dini Fridasari², Sekar Mega Oktavina²

¹ Lecturer of Kerta Cendekia Nursing Academy, Sidoarjo

² Student of Kerta Cendekia Nursing Academy, Sidoarjo

ABSTRACT

Health Promotion Activities with the title Clean and Healthy Lifestyle with Hand Washing at SDN Rangkah Kidul Sidoarjo Sidoarjo District Sidoarjo Regency is one form of community service in the form of counseling aimed at growing and improving healthy behavior in children from an early age, especially in PHBS Hand Washing. The implementation of these activities on November 15, 2018 took place at Elementary School of Rangkah Kidul, Sidoarjo District, Sidoarjo Regency. The target is students of Elementary School of Rangkah Kidul, Sidoarjo District, Sidoarjo Regency. Before the activity is carried out, there is a process of compiling the activity for 3 weeks before the activity is carried out, starting from the selection of health counseling materials to the submission of licensing to the relevant parties. As an evaluation, the activity was attended by 50 students and 2 teachers, participants participated in the activity with enthusiasm and conducive, the activity can be carried out on time smoothly.

Keywords: Hand washing, health promotion, elementary school, counseling.

INTRODUCTION

Washing hands is one of the sanitation measures by cleaning the hands and fingers by using water or antiseptic in other ways by humans in order to be clean, as part of religious rituals, or other purposes. Hand

washing behavior is different from hand washing behavior which refers to the figure of speech. New hand washing was recognized in the late 19th century with the aim of being healthy when sanitation behavior and services were the cause of a

sharp decline in mortality from infectious diseases in rich (developed) countries. this behavior was introduced in conjunction with the isolation and application of safe disposal techniques and the provision of sufficient quantities of clean water.

OBJECTIVES

General Purpose

After health promotion, the students of Elementary School of Rangkah Kidul, Sidoarjo District, Sidoarjo Regency can understand the importance of hand washing, especially for physical health.

Special Purpose

After conducting health promotion, it is expected that the students of Elementary School of Rangkah Kidul, Sidoarjo District, Sidoarjo Regency can:

1. Being able to know the meaning of washing hands.
2. Being able to know the consequences if not washing hands.
3. Being able to know anytime to wash hands.
4. Being able to know about handwashing animated images.
5. Being able to know about the importance of washing hands.
6. Mention and demonstrate the steps to wash hands again.

PLAN OF ACTION

Strategy Plan

The strategy plan implemented, including:

1. Coordinate with the principal of Rangkah Kidul Sidoarjo Elementary School, Sidoarjo District, Sidoarjo Regency to request permission to carry out health education or health promotion activities as a nursing program and to help give direction to

students of Elementary School of Rangkah Kidul, Sidoarjo District, Sidoarjo Regency.

2. Determine to students in the implementation of health education or counseling to know about PHBS washing hands.
3. Contracts with students at the Elementary School of Rangkah Kidul, Sidoarjo District, Sidoarjo Regency.
4. Providing health promotion about PHBS hand washing.

Implementation

Actions taken in the implementation of these activities, including:

1. Contacted the principal of the Elementary School of Rangkah Kidul, Sidoarjo Subdistrict, Sidoarjo Regency to request an activity permit and gathering the students of the Elementary School of Rangkah Kidul, Sidoarjo District, Sidoarjo Regency.
2. Prepare a place and health promotion media.
3. Students of the Elementary School of Rangkah Kidul, Sidoarjo District, Sidoarjo Regency, received counseling material.

Setting

This activity was carried out at the Elementary School of Rangkah Kidul, Sidoarjo District, Sidoarjo Regency.

Target

Target in this activity is all of the Students of Elementary School of Rangkah Kidul, Sidoarjo District, Sidoarjo Regency.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The activity starts at 08.00 WIB and ends at 09.30 WIB, when the health promotion is in accordance with the

planning. The activity was carried out at the Elementary School of Rangkah Kidul, Sidoarjo. There were 50 participants and 2 teachers. The participants seemed conducive and cooperative in the counseling activities. The activities were in the form of health education, discussion, question and answer, and distribution of leaflets about steps to wash hands.

Equipment used during the discussion was an animated drawing about washing hands, and leaflets. The use of language is very communicative and applicable in the delivery of health education, students respond fairly well to what has been delivered by the presenter. Teachers from the Elementary School of Rangkah Kidul, Sidoarjo were very enthusiastic and cooperated well during the counseling.

The questions asked by the presenters can be answered well by the participants. 90% of participants can practice hand washing steps.

CONCLUSION

Improvement of knowledge of students of elementary school of Rangkah Kidul, Sidoarjo on hand washing through health promotion was considered quite successful because almost all students were able to mention can mention the meaning of washing hands (75%), mention the impact if not washing hands (85%), follow the counseling material well (80%), and practice hand washing steps (90%).

REFERENCES

Saputra, A. (2012). *Pentingnya Menjaga Kesehatan dengan Cuci Tangan*.06. Retrieved from <http://fourseasonnews.blogspot.com/2012/06/pengertian-mencuci-tangan.html>

E.B. (2009). *Pendidikan dan Perilaku Kesehatan*. Retrieved from <http://adelinecalonperawat.blogspot.com/2009/03/sap-penyuluhan-cuci-tangan.html>

Anugrah, H. (2009). *Kesehatan Anank Usia Sekolah*. Retrieved from <http://anugerah.hendra.or.id/pasca-nikah/3-anak-anak/permasalahan-umum-kesehatan-anak-usia-sekolah/>

Notoatmodjo, S. (2003). *Pendidikan dan Perilaku Kesehatan*. Jakarta: PT Rineka Cipta

Notoatmodjo, S. (2005). *Metodologi Penelitian Kesehatan*. Jakarta: PT Rineka Cipta.

Notoatmojo, S. (2007). *Promosi Kesehatan dan Ilmu Perilaku*. Retrieved from <http://icoel.wordpress.com/kumpulan-skripsi/skripsi-2/>